

Accelerating Nigeria's Economy in the 21st Century Through Mechanized Production: A Thematic Approach

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Abstract

Accelerating Nigeria's economy in the 21st century through mechanized production is the bedrock of this study. Nigeria's government has recognized that enhancing her economy in the 21st century through mechanized production is a desideratum to attain solid and sustainable economic growth due to the instability and uncertainty in global crude oil prices. This research adopted secondary sources of data collection such as text books, journals, government documents etc and subsequently analyzed the data through the use of descriptive method of analysis also known as content analysis. The paper found out that farming systems currently practised in some parts of Nigeria do not encourage mechanized production. Majority of roads especially in the South Eastern part of Nigeria are not accessible. The paper recommends among others that Nigerian government should give utmost priority to road reconstruction in other to make them accessible to agricultural machines. The study concludes by asserting that if Nigeria fails to enhance her economy through mechanized, perhaps, she is announcing her economic doom.

Keywords: *Agriculture, Mechanization, Tractor, Food Security.*

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Introduction

Nigeria population is increasing at a fast rate of 2.56% annually (Oramah, 2006) and there is a need to improve Nigeria's economy in the 21st Century through mechanized production. Increase in agricultural production would arrest hunger and enhance the economy of the country in this challenging period. In his view, Ugochukwu (1999) posits that Nigeria is blessed with abundant fertile land which is yet to be exploited for mechanized production which would help to put these vast lands into cultivation thereby increasing agricultural productivity of the nation. Nigeria is blessed with many rivers which can be used for irrigation purpose for providing water for irrigation farming and there has been increase in training of manpower from Nigerian universities, polytechnics, monotechnics and colleges of education in order to provide the technical manpower for agricultural mechanization (Ugochukwu, 1999). He argued that there are availability of other technical knowledge and other farm facilities both within and outside Nigeria that can be utilized to improve mechanized production. More so, the earning from Nigeria petroleum industry can be utilized to fuel mechanized agriculture thereby improving Nigeria's economy.

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The journey of farming in Nigeria is very historic because of the multi-faceted nature of the country. Agriculture is a major sector of the Nigerian economy, accounting for up to 35% of total employment in 2020. According to Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), agriculture remains the foundation of the Nigerian economy, providing livelihoods for most Nigerians and generating millions of jobs (Ekere 2023). Along with crude oil, Nigeria relies on the agricultural products it exports to generate most of its national revenue. The agricultural sector in Nigeria comprises four sub-sectors: crop production, livestock, forestry, and fishing. Nigeria has a total agricultural area of 70.8 million hectares, of which 34 million hectares are arable land, 6.5 million hectares are used for permanent crops, and 30.3 million hectares are meadows and pastures (Okpoko, 2023).

In Nigeria, agricultural workers constitute an insignificant number in the country's population, but agriculture employs between 50 percent and 90 percent of the population for farming in the developing countries (Oduwole, 2018). According to the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation's website "three –quarters of the world's poorest people get their food and income by farming small plots of land about the size of football field (Drake, 2013).

What is the panacea to the daunting challenges of food insecurity and benefit from the plethora of financial gains and the multi-factorial tendencies inherent in the agricultural industry? The way forward to the question cited above is by intensifying the use of modern farm implements known as mechanized farm equipment on our farmlands (Uriri, 2019). Considering the fact that the agricultural industry directly affects so many industries, the benefits of intensifying mechanized farming will not be felt by the farmers and tractor owners alone. As a matter of fact, the nation has more to benefit from improved farming methods than the farmers (Uriri, 2019).

Till the present time, many small and medium-scale farmers have not adopted the use of modern farm implements in agriculture but still utilize crude system of farming which involves the use manpower for cultivating and harvesting on their farmland. With the adoption of these crude farm implements, that is the use of hoes, cutlass and other simple tools for commercial farming, it would be a herculean task for us to be a beneficiary of mechanized agriculture which is increased productivity. If care is not taking, it would also get to a point where it will become difficult to have a three square meal simply because the food items in circulation are continuously in low supply.

In advanced economies, mechanized production has contributed significantly in increased output and it has also played a major role in the advancement of their economy. The rationale behind this is that agriculture is not only for subsistence but also for commercial activities which generate revenue to the economy through export earnings. Agriculture is a significant aspect of any economy. However, available records reveal that Nigeria is one of the least mechanized countries in the world. The proportion to which Nigerian's adopts mechanized agriculture is rudimentary. A significant percentage of farmers still use crude farm tools of which the rate of productivity resulting from this is minimal (Akinboade, 2020).

In the 20th century, Central Bank Nigeria (CBN) report (1991) shows that agriculture was the main source of Nigeria's revenue, which contributed to about 42% of Gross Domestic Product as against 13% for Oil & Gas. Nigeria was a major supplier of agricultural products like cocoa, groundnut, palm oil and palm kernel, etc. This led to an increase in the country's GDP to 60%. However, with the passage of time (in the 1970's) there was economic diversification through oil; the focus of the economy was shifted from agriculture to petroleum, this neglect of agricultural sector led to a fall in the nation's GDP to 20% (Akinboade, 2020).

Mechanized production in the 21st century will significantly improve Nigeria's economy by reducing the cost of production of most raw materials used in the producing other finished and semi-finished goods, there will be a natural inflow of investors which will, in turn, create multiple employment opportunities for the teeming population.

Benefits of Mechanized Production on the Economy of Nigeria

Nigeria has been on mono economy for a long time because of its heavy reliance on petroleum (Bako et al, 2018). Due to instability and uncertainty in global the prices of oil, government of Nigeria, has realized the benefits of having a mono economy. Before the discovery of oil in 1956 in Nigeria, Nigeria was famous in her agrarian economy through which cash crops like palm produce, cocoa, rubber, timber, ground nuts, were exported, thus making Nigeria a major exporter in that respect. Also, Nigeria had 19 million heads of cattle, the largest in Africa (Adams, 2016). Without any contradiction of prejudice, petroleum has contributed tremendously to the revenue of the country since its discovery in 1956 and more especially, since 1970 when its price was on the upward trend, it is a well-known fact that Nigeria's continuous large earnings or revenue from this sector will be impossible due to the reduction in oil price. However, it is a known fact across the globe that for a country to attain growth and development, its economy has to be diversified (Adams, 2016). Therefore there is need to diversify Nigerian economy using mechanized production. According to Deere (2021) mechanized production is beneficial in the following ways:

Improved Techniques

Land reclamation has been improved, soil erosion has been reduced and irrigation systems are more efficient because of agricultural mechanization practices. Cultivators attached to tractors help to smooth out the soil, fill in ditches and remove weeds, which all help to increase the amount of land used and prevent soil from eroding, while irrigation can be more targeted to the roots of plants.

Commercialization

Subsistence farming has been significantly reduced by mechanized production and commercial agriculture has taken over, allowing for increased productivity and crop yields. This allows for more food to be produced on a much larger scale, even allowing for exports.

Nullifies Effects of Labor Shortages

In the countryside, where rural citizens have migrated to urban areas due to increased economic activity, labor shortages on farms are less of a problem because of the machines that can take on more agricultural tasks. Laborers also have to put in less time and effort to make farms functional because of mechanization.

Makes More Space for Crops

Land usage is significantly improved with this process because machines can make more challenging land arable that might previously have lain fallow. Also, land can be used more efficiently to grow a larger variety of crops and more of them.

Increases Farm Income

Mechanized production has also helped farms both small and large to earn more money on what they produce. First, time is saved by the mechanization process, which reduces the need to pay laborers over extended periods of time. Second, crop yields are higher, which results in more income. Third, it improves the profile of farms and helps them to work on a more global scale where they might have worked on a very small scale before.

Problems of Mechanized Production

Asiwajis (2023) posits that the daunting challenges facing mechanized production in Nigeria includes:

Poor Land Tenure System: This factor in Nigeria mitigates the progress thus far made in Agricultural mechanization. Farmers are not able to acquire more land to begin commercial farming. In Nigeria, the current land ownership act leads to too much division of farms. Agricultural mechanization hardly occurs in small farmland.

The poverty of Farmers/ Inadequate credit facilities: In Nigeria, many farmers live in hopelessness and poverty. They do not have the needed fund to acquire modern farming implements. The fact that farmers in Nigeria do have access to loan facilities makes this situation worse.

Scarcity of machinery: Farmers who can purchase expensive modernized farming implements face an obstacle. They import machinery outside the country, which means it costs more to procure them. This is one of the serious problems of agricultural mechanization in Nigeria.

Lack of infrastructure: Nigeria lacks the needed infrastructure to support mechanized farming. Infrastructures like good road networks, stable power supply, and ease of doing business are lacking in Nigeria. This means that these challenges will hinder the exportation of farm products.

Illiterate farmers: Most Farmers in Nigeria are illiterate. This implies they are oblivious to modern farming implement and procedures that can improve farm output. They may be unable to adopt mechanized production or use these farm devices (Asiwajis.com, 2023).

Poor agricultural policies: For decades, the government has only paid lip service to implement policies that could better the agricultural sector. The inability of the government to create policies that innovate and boost the productivity of farmers is one of the problems of mechanized production in Nigeria.

Methodology

For the purpose of generating data for this study, the researcher made use of documentary sources which is also known as “Secondary Sources” from related literature on accelerating Nigeria’s economy in the 21st century through mechanized production. By documentary sources, we mean any written material (whether hand-written, typed or printed) that is already in existence, which was produced for other purpose than the benefit of the investigator.

The researcher also utilized materials derived from both published and unpublished works such as text books, journals, periodicals, official documents, seminar and conference papers. We also made maximum use of internet in sourcing several useful information that form bulk of the data used to analyze this work. The internet sources were accessed using the Google and pdfgeni. This was done to generate information on the subject matter.

Discussion

Ajav (2000) opines that in advanced economies, mechanized production contributes significantly to increase in output which has helped their economy to break even. The rationale behind this is that agriculture is not only for consumption but for commercial activities to generate revenue for the country. Agriculture is the mainstay of a country but regrettably, Nigeria has not fully embraced mechanization. The rate to which Nigerians are knowledgeable about mechanized production is poor. A large number of farmers are still using crude farm implements which lead to low productivity. In the 20th century, agriculture was seen as the main income earner in Nigeria. Central Bank Nigeria’s (1991) reveals that agriculture contributed to about 42% of Gross Domestic Product as against 13% for Oil & Gas. In the Sub-Sahara Africa, Nigeria was the main

exporter of some agricultural products such as cocoa, groundnut, palm oil and palm kernel and among others. This increased the Nation's GDP to 60%. Unfortunately, in the 70's there was a total neglect of agriculture because of oil which formed the downstream sector. This neglect of agriculture because of petroleum led to a fall in the nation's GDP to 20% (Ajav, 2000).

Agriculture unarguably has suffered serious setback in terms of mechanization. Mechanized mechanization is the application of agricultural engineering principles, machines and technologies to the practice of agriculture, using mechanical systems, in food, fiber, fuel and also, in the production, processing, handling and storage of agricultural product. Food security is a major concern for every nation. Food security according to Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food which meets dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life (Ajav, 2000).

However, mechanized production is the panacea to the insecurity of food or shortage of food supply in Nigeria, simply because of increase in productivity associated with mechanization. Large agricultural output in Nigeria is facing with daunting challenges because the practice of peasant farming. Unfortunately, a higher percentage of the population largely depends on production from these peasant farmers who cultivate lands on a small scale with simple tools. In a report by Central Bank of Nigeria (1991), 95% of Nigerian farmers are peasant farmers who do not have the resources to cultivate on a large scale and only 5% farmers operate on a large scale (Ajav, 2000). They are also the major recipients of government supports. Hence, the peasant farmers who are the major stakeholders in the production of food for the nation are not able to produce enough food.

Through mechanized production, the country will be exposed to enough food and cash crops which are hitherto imported into the country. Hence, there will be no need to spend a considerable amount of foreign exchange on the importation of similar product.

Ever since we experienced the oil boom in the '70s, a large chunk of the nation's revenue has been from the sales of crude oil. Aside from the dangers of having a linear source of revenue, in recent years, the proceeds of crude oil have proven to be insufficient in the short and long run. To avert the intending disaster associated with over-reliance on a single commodity and improve our annual revenue in multiple folds, mechanized agriculture needs to be taken more seriously. Mechanized production unarguably will reduce the cost of producing most raw materials used in the production of other finished goods in Nigeria. Thus, there will be a natural inflow of investors which will invariably create multiple employment opportunities for the teeming population.

Citing from Ndubuisi (2019), mechanized production will definitely accelerate agricultural productivity in Nigeria which will invariably boost the available food in the country and reduce the rate of hunger in the country. With the adoption of mechanized agricultural practice, there will be season less or non-seasonal production of food, maturation periods of crops will be reduced due to increased agriculture and agricultural seed production and irrigation, There will be enough food for the teeming population of the country.

Mechanized farming system would improve the foreign exchange earning potential of the country. Excess farm produce (cash crops) as a result of commercial farming would be exported to other countries. He further asserted that agricultural mechanization increases the participation of the youth and the educated in farming activities. This is because it reduces the stress arid drudgery involved in farming. And also improves the profitability of farming ventures. This increases the interest of the masses in agriculture. Also, Agricultural mechanization also improves the shelf life of farm produce Ndubuisi (2019). It equally improves the processing and packaging of farm produce. These reduces food waste, And increases the prices of farm produce.

Mechanization is a strong input for agricultural crop production and one that historically has been neglected in the under-developed countries of the world. Factors that reduce the availability of farm power has an effect on the ability to cultivate sufficient land and have long been recognized as a source of poverty, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. Increasing the power supply to agriculture means that more tasks can be completed at the right time and greater areas can be farmed to produce greater quantities of crops while conserving natural resources. Applying new technologies that are environmentally friendly enables farmers to produce crops more efficiently by using less power (fao.org/sustainable-agricultural-mechanization, 2022).

Sustainable mechanized production can also contribute significantly to the development of value chains and food systems as it has the potential to render postharvest, processing and marketing activities and functions more efficient, effective and environmentally friendly. Increasing levels of mechanization does not necessarily mean big investments in tractors and other machinery. Farmers need to choose the most appropriate power source for any operation depending on the work to be done and on who is performing it. The level of mechanization should meet their needs effectively and efficiently. Women play an important role in many farming based communities, and in some countries, up to 80 percent of the total farm labour comes from women. This implies that power sources (human, animal or motor-based) need to be adapted to such necessities from an ergonomic, social, cultural and economic point of view. The reduction of drudgery is a key element of sustainable mechanization and contributes to reducing women's hard workload by taking into consideration technologies apt to their needs and improving their access to appropriate forms of farm power. Sustainable mechanization can: - increase land productivity by facilitating timeliness and quality of cultivation; - support opportunities that relieve the burden of labour shortages and enable households to withstand shocks better; - decrease the environmental footprint of agriculture when combined with adequate conservation agriculture practices; and reduce poverty and achieve food security while improving people's livelihoods (fao.org/sustainable-agricultural-mechanization, 2022).

Findings

From the discussion above, the study found out that:

1. Cultural practices in Nigeria constitute a very serious impediment to economic development. In many cases, people find it difficult to abandon their traditional agricultural system to mechanization. Hence, modernize agricultural practices including the use of improved seeds, farm implements, fertilizers and pesticides are seen as an exception rather than the contemporary development strategies. These traditional values conflict with industrialization and development.
2. Farmers lack the requisite knowledge of modern implements. This is why they find it extremely difficult to embrace mechanized production practice.
3. The level of mechanization to a large extent affects the operating incomes of different grain and cash crops. Hence, the final consumers bears the greatest burden due increment in the cost price.
4. A significant proportion of Nigerians have migrated to urban areas (rural – urban migration) in search of white collar jobs because machines undertake tasks which human beings ought to do.
5. The farming systems currently practised in some parts of Nigeria do not encourage mechanized production. Majority of roads especially in the South Eastern part of Nigeria are not accessible. It is expensive to hire machines, and most farmers are poor.

Recommendations

From the above discussion and findings, the study recommends that:

1. Cultural practices which can be best described as uneconomic should be deemphasized since it conflicts with economic development of Nigeria, so that farmers could be made more familiar with the benefits of improved crop varieties, increased use of fertilizers, increased water availability and proper rotation of crops.
2. More extension agents should be employed to educate farmers to accept and adopt modern farm techniques.
3. Government should emphasize the positive role of agricultural machinery in increasing agricultural efficiency and farmers' income. Mechanized production can effectively improve agricultural income. Increasing income is a basic requirement for the high-quality development of agriculture.
4. The practice of mechanized production should encourage people to go into agriculture instead of going elsewhere since problems encountered are reduced to the barest minimum because machines take on more agricultural tasks which increases agricultural productivity.
5. Nigerian government should give utmost priority to road reconstruction in other to make roads accessible to agricultural machines. Loans should be given to farmers to enable them purchase modern farm machines.

Conclusion

If Nigeria fails to enhance her economy through mechanized production, perhaps, she is announcing her economic doom. More importantly, to achieve sustainable mechanization, we need our own crop of entrepreneurs to seize the market and technical opportunities of the twenty-first century. Agriculture is by far one of the most important sectors of Nigeria's economy, engaging about 70 per cent of the labour force. But, farming is often of the subsistence variety, characterized by simple tools and shifting cultivation. Productivity has been hampered by the use of primitive tools and implements, lack of finance or credit facilities, poor transportation, inadequate land due to land tenure system, as well as inadequate agricultural education and extension services. The only thing that will save Nigeria from the quagmire of economic melt-down is the mechanization agriculture.

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